

Report on the third Delphi study results

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Report on the third Delphi study “Challenges and opportunities of the technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in open innovation ecosystem in developing transitional economies”

1. **Expertise structure:**

- Six entrepreneurs,
- Four environmental and sustainability managers,
- Four participants hold CEO or some managerial positions within their companies,
- Three technology officers,
- Three are data engineers or IT developers.

2. **Gender:**

- Thirteen participants are male, while seven participants are female.

First round of Delphi study results

After receiving the answers given by the respondents, their summarization follows, first at the level of each country, and then at the project level (the coordinators of each partner send summary answers to the questions to the project coordinator, and the coordinator summarizes them at the project level). The summary answers are the basis for creating a questionnaire for experts for the second round of research.

Coordinators by country deliver precisely defined statistics for each of the questions, namely:

1. Percentage of answers for YES/NO questions,
2. Summarized list (3 answers per expert, but in the final list included at least five answers with the highest frequency of appearances) to obtain a base for quantitative analysis in the next step.

1. All experts said that they are familiar with the open innovation ecosystem. When it comes to technology transfer 80% of the experts could define its main aspects. 95% of experts agree that active government practices toward supporting collaboration in research and innovation and knowledge spill over could offer benefits to businesses. Finally, 90% of experts claimed that they implement R&D activities in their company (organization).

2. The most frequent answers concerning other research questions are presented in the next table.

Table 1: Delphi study – answers systematized based on first round of interviews

Research objective (RO)	Questions
RO1	1. Can you define an open innovation ecosystem?* Yes 100%

RO1	<p>1a. How would you define and specify the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities, research institutions, and corporations. • Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations. • Government bodies that support funding and policy. • Investors and incubators providing financial support. • Academic institutions and organizations fostering innovation.
RO1	<p>2. What are the main aspects of effective open innovation management?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative culture. • Technological infrastructure. • Leadership and management. • Strategic partnership. • Striving for constant improvement.
RO1	<p>3. What are ways/factors to innovations' commercialization?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market access and marketing orientation. • Conferences. • Trade fairs. • Intellectual property rights. • Scientific journals. • Professional publications. • Industry associations. • Product adaptation
<p>4. Can you define the technology transfer aspects?* Yes 80%, No 20%</p>	
RO2 / 4	<p>4a. What are the challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of qualified workforce. • Insufficient financial resources and investments. • Weak collaboration between industry and research institutions. • Legal and regulatory challenges. • Lack of commercialization and market entry strategies.
RO2	<p>5. Which of these main aspects of technology transfer do you believe is the least developed in your country and why?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term collaboration between research institutions and companies. • Lack of financial resources for technology transfer (private investment, business angels) • Availability of grants and subsidies and tax incentives. • Costs and return on investment.
RO4	<p>6. Do you believe that active government practices toward supporting collaboration in research and innovation and knowledge spillover could offer benefits to your and/or other businesses?* Yes 95%, No 5%</p>

RO4	<p>6a. Describe at least three government practices that could boost and improve technology transfer in your country.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Government grants for research and innovation. 2. Collaboration between universities and companies. 3. Investment in research infrastructure and technology parks. 4. Tax incentives for research and development activities. 5. Public-private partnerships to stimulate innovation.
RO5	<p>7. Do you implement R&D activities in your company (organization)?* Yes 90%, No 10%</p>
RO5	<p>7a. Describe how you perform research and development activities (e.g., in your R&D department, in collaboration with external partners, etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with universities and external partners. • Establishing research centers focused on innovation. • Developing new technologies through R&D departments. • Conducting market research to guide product development. • Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners.
RO5	<p>8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)? If your organization collaborates on seeking innovative solutions, have you used inbound, outbound, or connected approaches to open innovation? Briefly describe.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We collaborate with universities and research institutions for joint projects. • We use internal R&D teams to develop new solutions. • We engage external experts to support innovation. • We apply open innovation by integrating external knowledge and ideas. • We collaborate with international partners to implement innovative technologies.
RO3	<p>9. Describe factors of intellectual property protection from your experience.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is necessary to have and implement national intellectual property law. • International agreements and conventions • Administrative procedures for rights protection. • Franchises and licenses. • Trademarks and design protection.
RO3	<p>10. Identify the key obstacles and challenges in the intellectual property protection system in your country.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs and complexity of the patent system. • Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights. • Insufficient enforcement mechanisms for IP protection. • Delays in registration of patents and trademarks. • Lack of harmonization with international IP standards. • Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards • Encouraging innovation while ensuring fair competition • Addressing piracy and counterfeiting effectively

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting cross-border cooperation and information sharing • Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge
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Source: Authors' presentation

Second round of Delphi study results

Based on the analysis of qualitative data obtained in the first round of empirical research, i.e. through in-depth interviews, but also on the basis of a previously prepared systematic literature review, an instrument is developed for the second round of research in the form of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to the same experts involved in the first round of the Delphi study to reach agreement on the key technology transfer challenges and needs from business sector in terms of academic or government support. In order to provide the efficiency of research, some questions were merged or modified due to the similar answers.

For each question that involves enumerating the answers, the experts declare themselves with grades from 1 to 5, using a Likert scale, whereby the experts are given an explanation of the grades according to the following meaning of the grade:

- 1 – Completely insignificant,
- 2 – Insignificant,
- 3 – Partially significant,
- 4 – Significantly,
- 5 – Very significant.

Table 2: Questionnaire for experts

Question	Answer				
	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
1. What are the key actors of an open innovation ecosystem?					
a) Universities and research institutions	1	2	3	4	5
b) Start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations.	1	2	3	4	5
c) Government bodies that support funding and policy.	1	2	3	4	5
d) Investors	1	2	3	4	5
e) Incubators	1	2	3	4	5

2. How significant are the following aspects for the implementation of open innovation strategies?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Innovation culture within the organization	1	2	3	4	5
b) Technological infrastructure	1	2	3	4	5
c) Leadership and management support	1	2	3	4	5
d) Strategic partnerships with other organizations	1	2	3	4	5
3. How significant are the following factors for successful commercialization of innovations?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Market access and marketing orientation of the organization	1	2	3	4	5
b) Intellectual property protection (patents protection, copyrights, trade secrets, industrial design rights, trademarks and branding)	1	2	3	4	5
c) Product adaptation to market needs	1	2	3	4	5
d) Partnerships with industrial entities	1	2	3	4	5
e) Support for entrepreneurship and start-up companies	1	2	3	4	5
4. What are the main challenges of technology transfer and sustainable entrepreneurship in the open innovation ecosystem in your country?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Lack of qualified workforce	1	2	3	4	5
b) Insufficient financial resources and investments	1	2	3	4	5
c) Weak collaboration between industry and research institutions	1	2	3	4	5

5. To what extent do the following financial factors influence technology transfer?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Availability of grants and subsidies	1	2	3	4	5
b) Opportunities for private investment	1	2	3	4	5
c) Access to angels' investors, venture capital and crowdfunding	1	2	3	4	5
d) Tax incentives for research and development	1	2	3	4	5
e) Costs and return on investment	1	2	3	4	5
6. To what extent are the following government incentives significant in supporting collaboration in technology transfer	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Tax credits and deductions for research and development activities	1	2	3	4	5
b) Grants and funding programs for collaborative research projects	1	2	3	4	5
c) Subsidies for technology commercialization efforts	1	2	3	4	5
d) Regulatory support and streamlined processes for intellectual property protection	1	2	3	4	5
7. How you perform R&D activities?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) Collaboration with universities and external partners	1	2	3	4	5
b) Establishing research centers focused on innovation	1	2	3	4	5
c) Developing new technologies through R&D departments	1	2	3	4	5

d) Conducting market research to guide product development	1	2	3	4	5
e) Participation in collaborative research projects with global partners	1	2	3	4	5
8. How do you implement innovative solutions in your company (organization)?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) We collaborate with universities and research institutions for joint projects	1	2	3	4	5
b) We use internal R&D teams for developing new solutions	1	2	3	4	5
c) We engage external experts to support innovation	1	2	3	4	5
d) We apply open innovation by integrating external knowledge and ideas.	1	2	3	4	5
e) We collaborate with international partners to implement innovative technologies.	1	2	3	4	5
9. How significant are the following legal and regulatory factors for intellectual property protection?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
a) National intellectual property laws	1	2	3	4	5
b) International agreements and conventions	1	2	3	4	5
c) Administrative procedures for rights protection	1	2	3	4	5
d) Franchises and licenses.	1	2	3	4	5
e) Trademarks and design protection.	1	2	3	4	5
10. How significant are the following obstacles and challenges in the intellectual property protection system?	1 - Completely insignificant	2 - Insignificant	3 - Partially significant	4 - Significant	5 - Very significant
Obstacles:					

a) High costs and complexity of the patent system.	1	2	3	4	5
b) Lack of awareness and education on intellectual property rights.	1	2	3	4	5
c) Insufficient enforcement mechanisms for IP protection.	1	2	3	4	5
d) Delays in registration of patents and trademarks.	1	2	3	4	5
e) Lack of harmonization with international IP standards.	1	2	3	4	5
Challenges:					
a) Harmonizing national IP laws with international standards	1	2	3	4	5
b) Encouraging innovation while ensuring fair competition					
c) Addressing piracy and counterfeiting effectively	1	2	3	4	5
d) Promoting cross-border cooperation and information sharing	1	2	3	4	5
e) Balancing the interests of IP holders with public access to knowledge	1	2	3	4	5

Source: Authors' presentation

USE IPM

The data collected in the second round are statistically processed. If more than 70% of the experts rated the offered answer as significant or very significant, it is considered that a consensus has been reached. The calculation is presented in the previous table.

The options within each question that reached the experts' consensus are qualified for the quantitative questionnaire. This Questionnaire is the basis of empirical research on a sample of at least 100 units (in all 4 countries) to identify the challenges in terms of technology transfer and intellectual property rights in the observed widening countries.